

and Q_4 which act as emitter followers. The square-wave-forms at the emitters of Q_3 and Q_4 are applied to the gates of S_1 and S_2 through current-limiting resistors R_7 and R_8 . The diodes, D_1 and D_2 , increase the turn-on voltage of each transistor by 0.7 volts, thereby preventing both transistors from getting turned on at the same time. The diode D_3 protects this circuit. When the square-wave is applied to the gate of the SCR, the gate current varies between zero and a fixed value (high enough to latch the device). When the gate current is zero, it is open, and when the gate current is large, it acts as a p-n diode. Since each solenoid is connected to an AC supply, with an SCR in series, the current flows in one direction in one-half cycle only. Due to the nature of the astable multivibrator, the wave-forms are complimentary and hence while one solenoid is on, the other remains cut off.

During normal operation, the pumping frequency is of the order of 40 to 50 oscillations per minute with an average displacement of about 5 cm.

We advise the following precautions in the construction of this pump: (1) each solenoid should have an equal number of turns, (2) since the current is inversely proportional to the number of turns, heating can be minimized by using as few turns as possible, (3) the piston should be made of soft iron rod, (4) the length of the piston should be 1-1/2 times the length of each solenoid and (5) teflon o-rings should be used to fit the piston to the glass tube as they provide minimum friction.

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Chemical Constituents of *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* Stem-Bark and Flowers

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IN an earlier publication¹, we have reported the isolation of gallic acid, ellagic acid, leucodelphi-

nidin and an ellagitannin from the stem bark of *C. pulcherrima*. Some other constituents present in the bark and flowers of this plant have now been investigated.

The hot ethanolic extract of the powdered bark was fractionated into (i) petroleum ether soluble; (ii) ether soluble and (iii) ethyl acetate soluble fraction. Fraction (i) yielded a steroid (A), fraction (ii) an acid (B) and fraction (iii) gave two compounds (C) and (D).

Compound (A) (β -sitosterol) :

It was isolated as white crystalline compound, m.p. 138°, (found: C, 83.92; H, 12.32%; Calc.: for $C_{28}H_{48}O$, C, 84.06; H, 12.08%). It gave all colour tests of steroids. It was identified as β -sitosterol by m.m.p. and co-chromatography with an authentic sample and also by its acetate and digitonide.

Compound (B) (Sebacic acid) :

This compound was isolated as white crystals, m.p. 130-32° (found, C, 59.32; H, 9.02%; Calc., for $C_{18}H_{34}O_2$: C, 59.40; H, 8.91%). Chemical tests indicated it to be a saturated aliphatic acid. Its IR spectrum was characteristic of a polymethylenic acid. It was identified as sebacic acid by m.m.p. and co-chromatography with an authentic sample and also by its amide formation.

Compound (C) (Quercetin-7-O- β -D(+)-glucopyranoside) (Quercimeritrin) :

The compound was isolated as pale yellow crystalline compound, m.p., 248-50° (d), (found, C, 54.37; H, 4.42%; Calc. for $C_{21}H_{20}O_{12}$: C, 54.31; H, 4.31%). It gave positive Molisch test and did not reduce Fehling solution, thereby indicating its glycosidic nature. Acid hydrolysis of the glycoside yielded an aglycone, $C_{15}H_{10}O_7$, m.p. 313-15° and a reducing sugar which was identified as D(+) glucose by mixed paper chromatography and osazone formation. Quantitative estimation of sugar showed it to be a monoglucoside.

The aglycone was found to be flavonoid in nature by its characteristic colour reactions. From its spectral studies (UV and IR) and preparation of derivatives i.e., acetate and methyl ether the aglycone was shown to be quercetin. Position of the glucose moiety was ascertained by taking shifts with different reagents in the ultraviolet region. A bathochromic shift of the long wavelength, band I with sodium acetate and boric acid² in ethanol with aglycone (18 nm) as well as glycoside (16 nm) suggested the presence of a free catechol unit in both. Aglycone and glycoside both gave bathochromic shift of long wavelength band I 58 nm and 54 nm respectively with ethanolic aluminium chloride³ showing thereby the presence of free 5-hydroxyl

group. The glycoside unlike the aglycone did not give any appreciable shift of the short wavelength band II with fused sodium acetate⁴ showing thereby the absence of free 7-OH group. Evidently the sugar was attached at position 7 of quercetin molecule. The formation of formic acid in the periodate oxidation of the methylated glycoside proved the pyranose ring structure for glucose. The nature of the glycosidic linkage as β was confirmed by hydrolysis with emulsin.

Based on the above data the glycoside could be identified as quercetin-7-O- β -D(+)-glucopyranoside or quercimeritrin. This glycoside has not so far been reported to occur in any other species of this genus.

Compound (D) (Leucodelphinidin) :

The compound was isolated as a buff coloured semi-crystalline solid. It was found to be a polyphenolic and sugar free entity. Pink colour with vanillin-HCl⁵ indicated the presence of free phloroglucinol unit. It gave dark magenta coloured solution on boiling with ethanolic hydrochloric acid which responded to all the colour reactions of naturally occurring 3-hydroxy anthocyanidins. The anthocyanidin had λ_{\max} 557 nm in ethanolic HCl (authentic delphinidin has λ_{\max} 560 nm) and gave bathochromic shift (23 nm) with aluminium chloride^{6,7} (vicinal hydroxyl groups). It was confirmed as delphinidin by cochromatography with an authentic sample. Therefore, the compound (D) λ_{\max} 282 nm and IR similar to the naturally occurring flavan-3 : 4-diols⁸ could be characterised as leucodelphinidin.

Anthocyanin from *Caesalpinia pulcherrima* flowers :

A chocolate coloured compound was isolated from 1% ethanolic hydrochloric acid extract of the yellowish pink flowers of *C. pulcherrima*. It gave positive Molisch test and other reactions characteristic of anthocyanins.

The glycoside on hydrolysis with 20% hydrochloric acid yielded an anthocyanidin which could be precipitated with petroleum ether from amyl alcohol solution into 1% aqueous HCl layer. It crystallised as dark reddish-brown prisms from ethanolic hydrochloric acid mixture and gave colour reactions specific of cyanidin.

The free sugar present in the hydrolysate was identified as D(+)-glucose by its osazone and cochromatography with an authentic sample. Quantitative sugar estimation showed it to be a diglycoside. The anthocyanidin had λ_{\max} at 545 nm (ethanolic HCl), authentic cyanidin has λ_{\max} at 545 nm. and exhibited bathochromic shift with $AlCl_3$ (presence of vicinal dihydroxyl groups). It was confirmed as cyanidin by co-chromatography with an authentic sample obtained from *Rosagallia* flowers. The anthocyanin had λ_{\max} 532 nm (ethanolic HCl). A hypsochromic shift of 13 nm in the glycoside as

compared to the aglycone was an indication of the probable position of the sugar at 3 & 5 nm. The anthocyanin also compared well with the authentic cyanidin-3 : 5 diglycoside (cyanin) isolated from *Rosa* galla flowers.

Therefore, the presence of cyanin (3:5-diglycoside of cyanidin) in *C. pulcherrima* flowers was confirmed.

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Chemical Investigation of Bark of *Abroma augusta* Linn. (Sterculiaceae).

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ABROMA *augusta* Linn. popularly known as 'Ulat Kambal' grows abundantly in the hotter parts of India. It is also available in the south-eastern region (Baliguni, Nanoor) of the district of Birbhum in West Bengal. The plant is medicinally very important and its roots and root-barks are used as emmenagogue, uterine tonic and in dysmenorrhoea¹. Locally (in the district of Birbhum) its leaves and stem-barks are extensively used in the treatment of gonorrhoea and in the unusually painful and difficult menstruation. The chemical investigation on the roots²⁻⁴ and leaves⁵ of this plant have already been reported but no phytochemical work